

Rethinking search intent: from traditional search engines to AI-powered information retrieval

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1. Introduction

The way users retrieve information has fundamentally changed in recent years. Traditional search engines (SEs), which once primarily acted as link aggregators directing users to external websites, have evolved into self-contained ecosystems. Modern search engine results pages (SERPs) increasingly provide direct answers through elements like featured snippets, knowledge panels, answer boxes, as well as multimedia content. These elements reduce the need for users to click through external websites to satisfy their information needs (Lewandowski, 2023; Oliveira & Teixeira Lopes, 2023).

Simultaneously, generative AI-based tools such as ChatGPT, Gemini, and Microsoft Copilot have entered the information retrieval landscape, enabling users to engage in conversational and generative interactions that shift how people seek and use information (Liu et al., 2024; Ouyang et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024). This shift is also evident in traditional SEs, which increasingly integrate large language models through Retrieval-Augmented Generation architectures (Bevara et al., 2025; Gupta et al., 2024). These systems combine document retrieval with generative capabilities to produce answer-like content often directly within the SERP, as seen in Google's AI Overviews and Microsoft's Bing Chat (Reid, 2024; Schwartz, 2025; TheBingTeam, 2025). As a result, users are no longer just navigating information but co-constructing it through interactive, system-mediated summaries, thereby redefining the scope of search tasks and how information needs are formed, refined, and satisfied (Suri et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2023).

Despite these fundamental changes, much of the research and system design in information retrieval continues to rely on frameworks developed in the early days of SEs. Particularly, the framework of search intent proposed by Broder (2002), which distinguishes between informational, navigational, and transactional intents, remains the most widely used by researchers to this day (Alexander et al., 2022; Jansen et al., 2008; Rose & Levinson, 2004; Shao et al., 2023). Broder's (2002) system-centered view conceptualizes user intent in terms of interactions with external websites, reflecting a period when the primary goal of search was to direct the user from the SE to a specific external resource (Broder, 2002; Jansen et al., 2008). Today, however, this model is increasingly misaligned with user practices, as modern SEs and AI tools often fulfill information needs directly within the platform, making destination-based interpretations insufficient (Kelly, 2025). We argue that relying on outdated intent categories risks leading to misrepresentation of how users search today. Effective system design and evaluation require a reconceptualization of search intent, namely one that centers on how users formulate and express their information needs, thereby calling for a shift toward a human-centered model (Bolger et al, 2003; Xie, 2002; Porta et al., 2014).

In this paper, we propose a revised intent taxonomy that overcomes the system-centered view of Broder's framework. We construct it based on a survey that asks participants to reflect on their recent interactions with SEs and AI chatbots, allowing for a more nuanced analysis of user intent. From these reflections, we identify intents that apply to both SEs and AI chatbots, accounting for emerging trends in the information retrieval landscape.

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2. Methodology

To capture user intent directly, we designed a survey ($N=86$, US-based) that prompts participants to reflect on their recent SE (85 Google, 1 Bing) and AI chatbot sessions (75 ChatGPT, 5 Gemini, 3 Claude, 3 Microsoft Copilot). Participants retrieve their last three sessions from their personal interaction histories, paste the initial query or prompt they used, and answer guided reflection questions about their goals (Xie, 2002), and how they used the obtained information. After performing a quality check, we retained 247 reflections on search sessions and 253 on AI chatbot conversations.

Our analysis follows a two-stage coding procedure (Braun & Clarke, 2006). First, we apply Broder's (2002) intent taxonomy deductively, categorizing sessions as informational, navigational, or transactional. This allows us to identify where the traditional framework remains relevant and where it shows limitations. Second, we conduct inductive coding, allowing new categories to emerge from the data based on the users' described information needs. We then contrast these emergent categories with the shortcomings of Broder's taxonomy to assess whether the new categories withstand these shortcomings.

3. Results and revised framework

Our deductive coding revealed substantial shortcomings in Broder's framework for the modern search landscape. Informational intent dominated both SE and chatbot sessions. This suggests that the classic intent division may no longer sufficiently differentiate user goals. In search sessions, the lines between navigational, informational, and transactional intents were often blurred. For example, with SERPs now displaying direct answers, it became unclear whether users intended to visit external websites or if the information provided within the SERP was sufficient. Similarly, transactional behaviors often merged with navigational and informational searches, as users gathered information or visited shopping sites before deciding to purchase or act, highlighting how user intent evolves throughout search sessions, which is not captured by traditional categories. In chatbot interactions, navigational intents were largely absent, reflecting the tools' focus on conversational support and content generation. These generative tasks, such as text and image creation, were not accounted for in traditional intent categories.

During the inductive coding phase, three distinct patterns emerged across SE and chatbot sessions. First, many sessions involved knowledge-seeking, where users sought objective information or real-time updates, such as explanations, definitions, or news. Second, guidance-seeking sessions were more contextual and exploratory, with users asking for advice, troubleshooting help, or personalized recommendations. Third, resource-seeking sessions focused on accessing specific resources or generating content, such as finding websites, services, or prompting AI chatbots for text or image creation.

In summary, we identified three key categories of user intent:

1. *Knowledge-seeking*: Searching for objective information or understanding of a topic.
2. *Guidance-seeking*: Requesting advice, troubleshooting, recommendations, or guidance for personal or practical issues.
3. *Resource-seeking*: Aiming to access specific resources or content.

Linking these new categories to Broder's limitations, the revised framework addresses several shortcomings. First, distinguishing knowledge-seeking from guidance-seeking captures meaningful differences within the previously broad informational category. Additionally, this split clarifies cases where informational and navigational intents overlap, such as when users search for advice in specific forums, now better reflecting users' underlying goals. Finally, the resource-seeking category resolves ambiguities between navigational and transactional intents by grouping sessions aimed at accessing

tools, services, or platforms. This category also includes requests for content generation, which were not captured in Broder's original taxonomy.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the limitations of traditional search intent taxonomies in capturing how users engage with modern search engines and AI chatbots. Through a survey-based approach, we ask participants to reflect on their recent interactions with these systems. Based on these reflections, we propose a revised search intent framework grounded in today's information-seeking practices. These findings provide a foundation for designing more user-centered retrieval systems and evaluation approaches.

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